

STRIDER NZAus Data Safety Monitoring Committee Charter

1. Introduction

This Charter is for the Data Safety Monitoring Committee (DSMC) for:

STRIDER NZAus: A randomised controlled trial of sildenafil therapy in dismal prognosis early-onset intrauterine growth restriction (New Zealand and Australia).

HRC reference: HRC 13/242

Trial Registration number: ACTRN 12612000584831

STRIDER NZAus is a multicentre randomised placebo controlled trial of sildenafil therapy recruiting women with severely growth restricted preterm fetuses across Maternal Fetal Medicine (MFM) centres in New Zealand and Australia. The primary aim of this study is to assess the effect of sildenafil compared to placebo on the growth velocity of the fetal abdominal circumference. The study is led by a team of investigators based at the University of Auckland (Dr Katie Groom, Professor Philip Baker, Professor Lesley McCowan, Professor Peter Stone and Dr Arier Lee). These investigators are working in collaboration with other similar studies planned worldwide and data will contribute to a planned individual patient data (IPD) analysis. Professor Philip Baker is a Co-Leader and Dr Katie Groom is a member of the IPD collaboration.

STRIDER NZAus will use an electronic database management service provided by the University of British Columbia (UBC), Canada. They will supply an electronic on-line randomisation service, trial drug management system and eCRF platform for data collection. This will ensure data is in a consistent format for compatibility with other studies in the IPD analysis. All data will be stored electronically and research and data management services provided by the UBC Clinical Trials Network (CTN). There are no pre-planned interim statistical analyses to assess the primary outcome.

The purpose of this document is to define the primary roles and responsibilities of the DSMC for the STRIDER NZAus trial only (not the STRIDER IPD analysis), its relationship with other trial committees, its membership and the purpose, format and timing of its meetings. The Charter will also provide the procedures for ensuring confidentiality and proper communication, the statistical monitoring guidelines for implementation by the DSMC, and an outline of the content of the Open and Closed Reports required by the DSMC. .

2. Primary Responsibilities of the DMC

The STRIDER NZAus DSMC will be responsible for safeguarding the interests of trial participants, assessing the safety and efficacy of the interventions during the trial, and for monitoring the overall conduct of the clinical trial. The DSMC will provide recommendations about stopping or continuing the trial. To contribute to enhancing the integrity of the trial, the DSMC may also formulate recommendations relating to the selection/recruitment of participants, their management, improving adherence to protocol-specified regimens and retention of participants, and the procedure for data management and quality control.

The DSMC will provide advice to the clinical trial leadership group, hereafter referred to as the Steering Committee (SC). The SC will be responsible for promptly reviewing the DSMC

recommendations, deciding whether to continue or terminate the trial; and determining whether amendments to the protocol or changes in study conduct are required.

The STRIDER NZAus DSMC will report to the HRC. The DSMC are required to act in accordance with the HRC Statutory and Standing Committees General Principles.

3. Organisational Diagram

The following diagram shows the relationships between DSMC and other committees and functional areas involved in the trial.

4. Membership of the DSMC

4.1 Members

The members of the STRIDER NZAus DSMC are as follows:

DSMC Chair Professor Caroline Crowther (Clinician and Trialist)
Liggins Institute
University of Auckland
Private Bag 92019, Auckland
Ph. (09)9236011
c.crowther@auckland.ac.nz

DSMC Members	Date Appointed to DSMC	Expertise	Location
Dr Jane Alsweiler	02/10/2013	Clinician, Neonatology	Newborn Services and Department of Paediatrics Auckland City Hospital and the University of Auckland
Dr Graham Parry	02/10/2013	Clinician, Obstetrician	Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Middlemore Hospital and the University of Auckland
Dr Yannan Jiang	28/04/2015	Statistician	Department of Statistics, Faculty of Science University of Auckland

The members of the STRIDER NZAus Trial Steering Committee are as follows:

SC Chair Dr Katie Groom (Clinician MFM and PI)
Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology
University of Auckland
Private Bag 92019, Auckland
Ph. (09) 373 7599 ext 89823
k.groom@auckland.ac.nz

SC Members	Expertise	Location
Professor Philip Baker	Clinician, Obstetrics	Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Auckland City Hospital and the University of Auckland
Professor Lesley McCowan	Clinician, MFM	Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Auckland City Hospital and the University of Auckland
Professor Peter Stone	Clinician, MFM	Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Auckland City Hospital and the University of Auckland
Dr Arier Lee	Biostatistician	Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics University of Auckland

4.2 Conflicts of Interest

The DSMC membership has been restricted to individuals free of apparent significant conflicts of interest. The source of these conflicts may be financial, scientific or regulatory in nature. Thus, neither study investigators nor individuals employed by the sponsor, nor individuals who might have regulatory responsibilities for the trial products, are members of the DSMC.

The DSMC members should be independent of the trial, and should not serve on DSMCs of similar concurrently active trials. They should not own stock in companies having products being evaluated by the clinical trial. Any competing interest, whether real or potential, should be declared. DSMC members must act in accordance with the State Services Commission Standards of Integrity and Conduct and the HRC Policy on Conflict of Interest.

The DSMC members will be responsible for advising fellow members of any changes in competing interests that occur during the course of the trial. Any DSMC members who develop significant conflicts of interest during the course of the trial should resign from the DSMC.

DSMC membership is to be for the duration of the clinical trial. If any member leaves the DSMC during the course of the trial the DSMC and the SC will promptly appoint a replacement.

5. Terms of reference and specific roles of the DSMC

Terms of reference

1. The DSMC will be responsible for safeguarding the interests of trial participants, assessing the safety and efficacy of the interventions during the trial, and for monitoring the overall conduct of the clinical trial.
2. To provide protocol advisory review.
3. To provide both recommendations based on the progress and accruing data of the trial and advice on the conduct of the trial to the SC. This will include a recommendation about stopping or continuing the trial.
4. To offer comment on the final results of the study, in order to provide any additional insights which may have been gained through the monitoring process.
5. To monitor and provide recommendations that will enhance the integrity and credibility of the study.

Specific roles of the STRIDER NZAus DSMC

To undertake to review the trial's progress by:

- Assessing data quality, including completeness
- Monitoring recruitment figures and losses to follow-up
- Monitoring compliance with the protocol by participants and investigators
- Monitoring randomisation and stratification balance.
- Monitoring evidence for treatment differences in efficacy and safety outcome measures
- Monitoring evidence for treatment harm in a timely way, receiving prompt reports of SUSARs (SAEs that are unexpected and may be related to study drug) and taking appropriate action to ensure patients' safety
- Recommending whether the trial should continue to recruit or follow-up (see section on recommendations to the SC)
- Recommending any major changes to the protocol where necessary (e.g. changes to recruitment procedures, inclusion criteria, endpoints, data collection)
- Advising on and/or endorsing any major protocol modifications suggested by the investigators
- Assessing the impact and relevance of any external evidence provided

- Monitoring the compliance with previous DSMC recommendations
- Considering the ethical implications of any recommendations made by the DSMC

The DSMC will report its recommendations to the SC. If the DSMC has serious concerns with a SC decision following DSMC recommendations, a meeting of these two groups will be held. If required confidential data may be revealed to all those attending such a meeting. The meeting will be chaired by an external expert not directly involved with the trial and who is agreed upon by both the DSMC Chair and the Principal Investigator. If necessary the DSMC will send their recommendations, with the SC responses and DSMC review of the appropriateness of the SC responses, to the HRC, the STRIDER IPD DSMB and the NZ HDEC and appropriate Australian Ethics Committees.

All DSMC members will have sight of the protocol/outline before agreeing to join the DSMC. DSMC members should be constructively critical of the on-going trial, but supportive of the aims and methods of the trial.

6. Timing and Purpose of the DSMC Meetings

6.1 Organisational Meeting

The initial meeting of the DSMC will be an Organisational Meeting. It will be held to discuss the standard operating procedures for the role and functioning of the DSMC, and to discuss the format and content of the Open and Closed Reports that will be used to present trial results at future DSMC meetings.

The Organisational Meeting will be attended by the DSMC, the lead trial investigator, the trial statistician, and the trial manager. Before the meeting, the DSMC will be provided with the clinical trial protocol, the Statistical Analysis Plan, the DSMC Charter, and the current version of the case report forms (CRFs). The DSMC will also receive the initial draft templates of the Open and Closed Reports. Agreement on the format and content of reports will ensure the DSMC is receiving the necessary data on the trial progress.

6.2 Monitoring meetings

DSMC monitoring meetings will take place every 6 months. At least one meeting per year should be in person. The Principal Investigator (PI), or nominee, must attend (or be available to attend) open sessions of the DSMC meetings. Other members of the SC and the trial manager may also attend the open sessions.

The trial statistician will be responsible for preparation of DSMC reports. This will provide the link between the database and the DSMC. The trial statistician will be the only person outside the DSMC to have access to unblinded data (data from closed reports) during the trial. However the trial statistician will not be present for or involved in discussion of the reports. The trial statistician will receive data directly from the data management team at UBC and will be responsible for finalising the open and closed DSMC reports. The trial statistician will not attend the DSMC meeting.

The first meeting of the DSMC will take place during the early stage of recruitment, to review early safety information, to review factors relating to quality of trial conduct, and to review information provided to the DSMC. No formal interim statistical analysis of the primary outcome is planned.

Every effort should be made for all DSMC members and the trial PI to attend meetings. If, at short notice, any DSMC member cannot attend, the meeting may still take place as long as a quorum of three people is present, including the DSMC Chair. If the DSMC is considering recommending a major action after such a meeting the DSMC Chair should talk to the absent members as soon as possible after the meeting to confirm agreement. If consensus cannot be reached, a further meeting by teleconference with the full DSMC should be held.

7. Procedures to Ensure Confidentiality and Proper Communication

To enhance the integrity and credibility of the trial, procedures will be implemented to ensure the DSMC has sole access to evolving information from the clinical trial regarding comparative efficacy and safety data (aggregated by treatment arm if required). An exception will be made to permit access for the trial statistician who will be responsible for preparation of the DSMC reports. The DSMC Chair will be provided immediate access on an on-going basis to patient-specific information on Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reactions (SUSARs) and report of all SUSARs must be made to the DSMC Chair no later than 5 working days after the event becomes known to the PI and/or trial manager.

Open Sessions and Closed Sessions will be implemented to provide a forum for exchange of information among the parties who share responsibility for the successful conduct of the trial. The intent of this format is to enable the DSMC to preserve confidentiality of the comparative efficacy results while at the same time providing opportunities for interaction between the DSMC and Trial investigators who have valuable insights into trial-related issues.

7.1 Closed Sessions

Sessions involving only DSMC members (called Closed Sessions) will be held to allow discussion of confidential data from the clinical trial, including information about the relative efficacy and safety of interventions. In order to ensure that the DSMC will be fully informed in its primary mission of safeguarding the interest of participating patients, the DSMC may be unblinded in its assessment of safety and efficacy data if determined necessary.

After the following Open Session, a final Closed session will reconvene for the DSMC to develop a consensus on its list of recommendations, including that relating to whether the trial should continue.

7.2 Open Session

In order to allow the DSMC to have adequate access to information provided by trial investigators, a joint session between trial investigators and DSMC members (called an Open Session) may be held between the Closed Sessions. This session gives the DSMC an opportunity to query trial investigators about issues that have arisen during their review in the initial Closed Session. This allows important interactions to be facilitated through which problems affecting trial integrity can be identified and resolved. Trial investigators will either be present in person at the DSMC meeting or by telephone link.

Where new external evidence (e.g. from other trials or systematic reviews) pertains to the trial, the Principal Investigator will take responsibility to collate such information and provide it to the DSMC in advance of DSMC meetings for discussion during the Open Session.

7.3 Open and Closed Reports

For each DSMC meeting, Open and Closed Reports will be provided (See Section 8 for outlines of the content of these reports). The trial statistician will provide the finalised reports (after receiving data from UBC).

Open Reports, available to all who attend the DSMC meeting, will include data on recruitment and baseline characteristics, eligibility violations, completeness of follow-up and compliance (overall and site specific).

Closed Reports, available only to those attending the Closed Sessions of the DSMC meeting, will include analyses of pre-specified efficacy endpoints, analyses of AEs and SAEs, and Open Report analyses. Inclusion criteria stratification factors will be reported by intervention group. Other data will initially be presented as overall group data, if after review of the closed reports it is determined that efficacy and safety data should be reviewed by intervention group the meeting will be reconvened to allow preparation of the Closed Report by intervention group. At this time the DSMC will have the option to reveal treatment allocation if deemed necessary.

The Open and Closed Reports should provide information that is accurate, with follow-up that is complete to within two months of the date of the DSMC meeting.

7.4 Minutes of the DSMC Meeting

Minutes will be taken by a nominated member of the DSMC and kept securely by the DSMC Chair. Two sets will be prepared: the Open Minutes and the Closed Minutes.

The Open Minutes will describe the proceedings in the Open Session of the DSMC meeting. These minutes will be circulated in a timely manner to the Principal Investigator and the study statistician. The Principal Investigator is responsible for distribution of the Open Minutes to other members of the SC. It is necessary that these minutes do not unblind the efficacy and safety data if the DSMC is not recommending early termination.

The Closed Minutes will describe the proceedings from all sessions of the DSMC meeting, including the listing of recommendations by the Committee. Because it is possible that these minutes may contain unblinded information, it is important that they are not made available to anyone outside the DSMC. Copies will be archived by the DSMC Chair for distribution to the Principal Investigator, and regulatory authorities at the time of study closure.

7.5 Recommendations to the Steering Committee (SC)

At each meeting of the DSMC during the conduct of the trial, the DSMC will make a recommendation to the SC to continue or to terminate the trial. This recommendation will be based primarily on

safety and efficacy considerations and will be guided by statistical monitoring guidelines defined in the Charter.

The SC is jointly responsible with the DSMC for safeguarding the interests of participating patients and for the conduct of the trial. Recommendations to amend the protocol or conduct of the study made by the DSMC will be considered and accepted or rejected by the SC. The SC will be responsible for deciding whether to continue or to stop the trial based on the DSMC recommendations.

The SC will provide responses to DSMC recommendations within 25 working days of receipt of the recommendations. These responses will be sent to the DSMC Chair. The DSMC will, if necessary, forward copies of DSMC recommendations and the responses to those recommendations to the HRC (as primary trial sponsor) and the appropriate Ethics Committees, along with a brief comment on DSMC concurrence with the response. (In particular where DSMC recommendations are not adopted, the DSMC will comment on whether or not they consider the justification provided by the SC adequate).

The DSMC must be notified of all proposed changes to the protocol or to study conduct. DSMC consensus must be sought on all substantive changes to the protocol or study conduct prior to their implementation.

7.6 HRC Reporting Requirements

Each meeting of the STRIDER NZAus DSMC will be reported to the HRC. Any recommendation to stop a trial must be reported to the HRC Board.

Any issues of risk to trial participants, trial integrity, or to the HRC must be raised at these meetings and, if necessary, the HRC will be informed.

8. Statistical Monitoring Guidelines

8.1 Early termination for benefit

The DSMC will not recommend that the trial be stopped purely for efficacy reasons. Early termination for benefit is not set for this trial as the trial is not powered to detect an early statistically significant benefit. In order to determine whether true benefit exists complete trial recruitment is necessary.

8.2 Early termination when evidence indicates the experimental intervention has an unfavourable benefit-to-risk profile

The DSMC may recommend that the trial be stopped for safety reasons or where a clear and significant unfavourable benefit-to-risk profile is present for the sildenafil treatment group based on the following endpoints:

- Stillbirth rate
- Neonatal death rate

- Prolongation of pregnancy (randomisation to delivery interval)

8.3 Sample size adjustment

An interim analysis is not planned for this trial; subsequently sample size adjustment will not be considered by the DSMC.

9. Content of DSMC's Open and Closed Reports

9.1 Open Statistical Report: An Outline

- Brief outline of the study design
- Statistical commentary explaining issues presented in Open Report figures and table
- DSMC monitoring plan and summary of Open Report data presented at prior DSMC meetings
- Major protocol changes
- Study accrual by month and by institution
- Eligibility violations
- Recruits per inclusion criteria
- Baseline characteristics
 - Demographics
 - Gestational age at recruitment
 - Presence or absence of EDF in UA Doppler
 - Presence of maternal preeclampsia
- Adherence to study drug schedule (pooled by treatment group), including: compliance, any dosing errors such as subject being given the wrong bottle number/type.
- Adherence at scheduled antenatal visits (pooled by treatment regimen)
- Completeness of data (pooled by treatment regimen)

9.2 Closed Statistical Report: An Outline

- Statistical commentary explaining issues raised by Closed Report figures and tables (only by coded treatment group if deemed necessary after initial review, with codes to allow unblinding sent to DSMC members by a separate mailing)
- DSMC monitoring plan and summary of Closed Report data presented at prior DSMC meetings
- Repeat of the Open Report information, by treatment group if requested
- Analyses of pre-specified efficacy endpoints overall (only by treatment group if requested)
 - Stillbirth rate
 - Neonatal death rate to time of hospital discharge
 - Prolongation of pregnancy (randomisation to delivery interval)
- Analyses of safety data overall (only by treatment group if requested)
 - Adverse events (AEs)
 - Expected serious adverse events (SAEs); unrelated to study drug

- Expected serious adverse reactions (SARs); possibly, probably or definitely related to study drug
- Unexpected SAE; unrelated to study drug
- Suspected unexpected serious adverse reaction (SUSAR); possibly, probably or definitely related to study drug
- Unplanned discontinuation of study drug